

IGBO COSMOLOGY OF DEATH AS EXPRESSED IN SOME SELECTED IGBO FOLK SONGS.

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ABSTRACT

The traditional Igbo society though deficient in written tradition employed different oral means such as: folksongs, folktales, proverbs, histories, legends, myths, drama etc in explaining the realities among them. Death is one of those realities that have continued to receive widespread explanation in Igbo culture. The mention of death in Igbo culture fascinates and frightens the broad range of humanity. This work therefore explored and studied the Igbo metaphysical sense of death as expressed through some selected folk songs. The work strived toward a musical cum anthropological analysis of some Igbo concepts of death composed in songs. The bulk of data (folksongs) gathered for the research were analysed using the analytical method of data analysis.

Introduction

In Igbo cosmology, life and death are intimately connected. Life as well as death permeates the African existential world. No wonder an Igbo adage says: “the wooden gong calls twice on the great man: in life and in death”(*ugboro abuo ka ekwe na akpo dike: o kpoo ya na ndu o kpoo ya n'onwu*).

Life has an inestimable value in Igbo culture. For the Igbo people, life is first (*ndubuisi*), life is greater than wealth (*ndukaku*). As a matter of fact, one of the highest gift from God to man is life. No wonder why the Igbo meaning of man is (*mma- ndu* – beauty of life).

There are two stages of life in Igbo culture: the physical and the spiritual or ancestral life. Death therefore, is considered as the only means or pathway through which the transition from physical world to spiritual or ancestral world is done. Death paves the way to new birth and makes affiliation to the ancestral abode possible. However, the pain of separation and the termination of social and familial bond with the deceased make death a painful reality. According to Igbo mythology, death could have been avoided if not for the carelessness of the dog. The myth has it that the dog and the tortoise were sent by men to God with different messages. The dog was to deliver the message of those who do not want death on earth while the tortoise was to deliver the message of those who want death on earth. The dog being faster than the tortoise ran ahead of him but was carried away by the distraction on the way and diverted elsewhere making the tortoise to reach before him. God received the message of the tortoise and approved death for men.

These realities about death and other realities of life that has latent psychological, psychical and spiritualizing essence form the basis of Igbo worldview. Music therefore serves as one of the avenues through which the Igbo man communicates and passes these realities of life. That is why African culture is not complete without music. The Igbo people are great lovers and makers of music. They cannot gather without making music. As a matter of fact, every of their activities go with music. Gatherings during funerals are replete with songs about as will be exposed in this write-up.

THE IGBO ETHNIC GROUP OF NIGERIA AND THEIR RICH CULTURAL HERITAGE

The Igbo ethnic group is the second largest group of people living in southern Nigeria. They are one of the three major tribes in Nigeria. They consist of many subgroups and are known to be socially and culturally diverse. Although Igbo people are mostly Christians, they have a deep and original culture. Igbo culture includes the various customs, practices and traditions of the people. It comprises ancient practices as well as modern concepts added into the Igbo culture either through evolution or outside influences. These customs and traditions include the Igbo people's visual art, religious beliefs, birth, marriage and death rituals, use of language, music and dance forms, as well as their attire, cuisine(food) and language dialects.

Geographically, the Igbo homeland is divided into two unequal sections by the Niger River – an Eastern (which is the larger of the two) and a Western section. The Igbo people are one of

the largest ethnic groups in Africa. In rural Nigeria, Igbo people work mostly as craftsmen, farmers and traders. The most important crop is the yam. Other staple crops include cassava and yam. The Igbo land are also highly urbanized, with some of the largest metropolitan areas, cities and towns in Igboland like: Onitsha, Enugu, Aba, Owerri, Orlu, Okigwe, Asaba, Awka, Nsukka, Nnewi, Umuahia, Abakaliki, Afikpo, Agbor and Arochukwu

THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN TRADITIONAL IGBO SOCIETY.

Traditionally, music plays an important role in Igbo culture. It is essential in representing the strong Igbo heritage and its importance can be seen in many aspects of the culture. Unlike many cultures today, ancient African cultures encompassed music into their everyday lives. Dance, story-telling and religious practices are all grounded on the music of the culture. Music in Igbo land is a way of life and not just a form of entertainment. It forms an integral part of their culture, with various ceremonies being preceded by some sort of music. Music is used to communicate, welcome heroes and other ritual functions.

IGBO FOLK SONGS

Igbo Folk songs are traditional or indigenous songs of Igbo society composed by ordinary people. The songs are not written down but are passed from one generation to another orally. Echezona (1966) asserts that folk songs composition do not require the technicalities involved in the composition of modern songs by modern trained composers. Rather they are native product, springing almost unconsciously from the hearts of simple people, and not intended to convey any such definite expression of the meaning of the words as is conveyed in modern songs. Hence, folk songs according to Agu(1989) naturally reflect the musical idioms of its people.

Most of the stories told in various communities are suddenly converted into music as the people gather together from time to time.

The folk song of a people has a deep impression on the welfare of the people. A folk singer expresses his happiness, hatred and all worries of life in the kind of song he or she sings. Most of the good and bad happenings in a society are related to outsiders and people within through songs. No wonder Nzewi (1980) describes the Nigerian traditional folk song as something that has latent psychological, psychical and spiritualizing essence because it plays a vital role in all important stages of life of the average Nigerian viz: birth, puberty, marriage, title-taking, initiation into social and cult groups and death .

Igbo Folk songs play recreational, ceremonial, entertainment and didactic roles in the society.

IGBO COSMOLOGY ON DEATH AS EXPRESSED IN SOME SELECTED FOLK SONGS.

1. DEATH IS PAINFUL

For the Igbo culture, the demise of a friend, relative and more so that of a family person, is a very painful occurrence. This is because of the way Africans bond with their friends, and especially with members of their family. The result is that there is a lot of emotional display including weeping and wailing.

Accordingly, neighbours and friends visit the deceased to condole and sympathise with them. Those consolatory words to the family of the departed are put into songs thus:

DIBE DIBE

Folk song

Igbo translation

*Dibe Dibe Dibe,
ndidi ka mma
Ony' omelu ya dibe e
ndidi kamma.*

English Translation

Be patient, be patient,
For patience is better
To whomever it happens
Let him be patient,
For patience is better.

2. DEATH IS A THIEF

Certain experiences about death have led to the personification of death as a figure or a fictional character in Igbo culture. For instance, the sudden and unannounced visit of death which is analogous to the action of a thief has made the Igbo people to personify death as a thief. This personification of death as a thief is seen in this folk song:

ONWU BU ONYE ORI

Folk song

Igbo translation

Onwu bu onye olio o

Onwu bu onye olio o

O bulu ogbanaga

English translation

Death is a thief

It steals and runs away.

3. DEATH LEAVES A VACUUM.

Death creates a vacuum that no other person can fill. It is that painful vacuum that inspired the composition of the folk song below.

Anyi na acho nwanne anyi

Folk song

Igbo translation

Anyi na-acho nwanne

Nwanne anyi onye obioma eh

Olee mgbe k'anyi ga-ahu ya

Onwu e mee anyi aru

K'o diba

English translation

We are looking for our brother,

Our brother who is kind hearted

Where shall we see him again

Death has dealt seriously with us

Till we see again.

4. DEATH TAKES NO BRIBE AND GIVES NO ROOM FOR NEGOTIATIONS.

Igbo cosmology acknowledges the far-reaching effect of the power of death as something that is mean and firm. It does not give room for negotiations, neither does it collect bribe. Some

centric names like *onwu-ama-enyi* (death knows no friend); *onwu-ana-ego* (death does not take money), and *Onwu-kwe* (if death agrees) explain the above. This folk song expresses the desire that

Onwu i mara buru ego

folk song

O-nwui - ma-ra bu-r'e - go ha - pu - r'a - nyi nwan - nea - nyi _____ o-nwui-

6
ma - ra bu - r'e - go ha - pu - r'a - nyi nwan - nea - nyi _____

Igbo translation

Onwu I mara buru ego

Hapuru anyi nwanne anyi (2X)

English Translation

Death, you would have taken money

Leaving our brother

5. DEATH IS INEVITABLE AND UNAVOIDABLE.

To an average human being, death is by no means a pleasant topic for discussion. Many wish it away while others postpone the talk of it or even wish others were involved in it not themselves. In this case, they are less perturbed when they hear the news of death in their neighbourhood. They would rather prefer going for their personal business than identifying with the deceased. This folk song therefore advice such people of laissez faire attitude that death is inevitable. No one runs away from death. Proverbially, “death is a debt which everyone owes” (*onwu bu ugwo madu ji*).

O nuru onu onwu

folk song

O nu-ruo - nuo - nwu bu-lun - ka - ta je - beO - ni - cham - gbe - re O

6
zu - chaa nya lo - ta e o bu - zio - fuo - nye nwe o - nwu

Igbo translation

O nuru onu onwu

Buru nkata jebe onicha mgbere

O zuchaa nya lota e

O buzi ofu onye nwe onwu

English Translation

He/She who hears the cry of death

And carries his basket to Onitsha market
for business

After the market, he should come home

Death is waiting for him.

6. UNNATURAL DEATHS ARE MORE PAINFUL THAN NATURAL DEATH.

Despite the belief in the inevitability of death, the Igbo people still categorise death into two: natural and unnatural death. When death comes to an elder who is seen to have left a good legacy in terms of morality and charity, responded to the law of procreation, it is said to be natural (*onwu chi*).

The Igbo tradition accepts that it is only those who die a natural death that can access the fullness of life in the ancestral world. Such person is given a befitting burial and funeral as a rite of passage to the ancestors.

However, certain deaths like that of a child or a middle aged person, death through accident are regarded as unnatural. It is believed that such persons have not yet completed their assignments on earth before death struck. The funeral of those who died unnatural death is not celebrated but rushed. These Folk songs are sung during such funerals:

UGOGBE TIWARA N' IKE

Folk Song

Igbo translation

Ugogbe etiwaana, o tiwaana

Nnukwu ugogbe etiwaana, o tiwaana, O

tiwara n'ike

English translation

The mirror has shattered

Great mirror has shattered

It shattered unexpectedly.

O nwuru n'ike

folk song

O nwu-ru n'i - ke n'i - kea - nyi g'a - kwa ya n'i - ke n'i - ke

5
O nwu-ru n'i - ke n'i - kea - nyi g'a - kwa ya n'i - ke n'i - ke

Igbo translation

O nwuru n'ike n'ike

Anyi g'akwa ya n'ike n'ike

English translation

He died suddenly

We will bury him suddenly 2x

CONCLUSION

Having come this far in this reflection about death, we can deduce that death from Igbo perspective is not an end. It marks a transition to “the other beginning.” Martin Heidegger pointed out that Man is a “being unto death,” And this death is enigmatic, a mystery, and a reality beyond full human comprehension.

However, the inevitability of death, however, does not lead the Igbo to despair and fear. Rather it calls for an effort to reflect on the meaning of existence.

All those folk songs rendered during funerals help in consoling the bereaved. Thus, according to Nzewi (1980),...those folk songs demonstrate the Igbo concept of dirge as a special musical means of soothing the grief of a bereaved. The dirge singer relieves the bereaved of the burden of excessive weeping and other cathartic forms.

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